

Resources, Representations and Reasoning: Young Children’s Analytic Approaches in Solving Number Tasks

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This paper presents and discusses some findings of an intervention with first class boys investigating their use of mathematical resources and representations to aid and highlight mathematical reasoning. Across a series of reasoning tasks in the area of number, the boys were encouraged to solve, represent and discuss their solution attempts. Some interesting features of reason arose in this study. Children drew on mathematical resources and representations made available to them to aid and present further mathematical reasoning. In some cases, they extended this reasoning to evaluate the usefulness of particular resources and justify their adoption or rejection of them as well as to justify their choice of representations in line with their need for support as they moved toward mental methods. Some examples of the children’s use of representations and reasoning are presented, with a focus on evaluation of representations as to the most mathematically appropriate and useful representations.

Reasoning and Representations

Mathematical reasoning is a complex cognitive process, which depends on knowledge and understanding. It involves the use of mathematical evidence and facts to support conclusions (Sarama & Clements, 2009). It stems from careful consideration of alternatives, and includes knowledge of how to justify conclusions (Kilpatrick, et al., 2001). A process of “noting patterns, generalizing relationships, making conjectures, questioning, and evaluating or constructing arguments and ideas” is necessary for the development of reasoning skills. Mathematical reasoning is an integral part of doing mathematics (Chapin et al., 2009, p. 78). It includes not only informal explanations and justifications but also intuitive and inductive reasoning based on pattern and analogy (Kilpatrick et al., 2001). The legitimacy of reasoning can be supported by discussing concepts and procedures; by representing problems, solutions and their understanding of mathematics in multiple ways; and by offering good reasons for the procedures and strategies they employ (NCCA, 2017).

Many forms of representations exist to convey mathematical ideas and develop reasoning skills: pictures, concrete materials, tables, graphs, diagrams, equations and symbols are just some of the forms used by mathematicians (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2000; Lesh, Post and Behr, 1987). The process of organizing, recording and communicating mathematical ideas is aided by manipulation of objects or diagrams (Turner, 2013). An aid to seeing relationships in mathematics, materials are 'picturable' in that they can be remembered through mental imagery rather than through a word or symbol, which helps children to internalise their experience (Resnick & Ford, 1981). Representations can be used as tools to help record mathematical ideas, communicate thoughts and clarify understandings (Chapin et al., 2009). It is important for children to manipulate ideas to make connections between different representations as interacting with resources supports children in the process of discovery and in constructing meaningful understanding. These experiences can be

enriched by teacher support eliciting and supporting children's mathematical connections (Turner, 2013).

Representational systems can be considered as vehicles of thought in mathematics (Nickerson, 2009). Representations highlight specific aspects of a mathematical concept which can support the process of explanation and develop understanding (Kaput, 1991; Ainsworth, 1990). Where representations appropriately capture mathematical concepts, then they can be used as tools to model and describe mathematical meaning and understanding and therefore promote the development of reasoning skills.

Mathematical Discussion

Just as representations do not contain but display mathematics, language does not transport knowledge but is a very powerful tool to orient children's conceptual construction by engaging them in discussion and explanation (Von Glasersfeld, 1991). According to Walshaw and Anthony (2008), mathematical discourse makes students' reasoning visible and open for reflection. Teachers play a role in engaging students in thoughtful mathematical conversations to develop explanations, make predictions, debate alternative approaches, clarify, or justify their thinking" (Brophy, 2001, p. 13). When learners engage in mathematical conversations they construct and improve their understanding through the exploration of ideas. Walshaw and Anthony (2008) state that environments where thoughts are shared enable students' own ideas to become resources for their learning. This makes it possible for them to communicate, reflect on, and evaluate their own and others ideas. The interplay between engaging with and evaluating mathematical reasoning and representing, through expertly guided discussion, creates an environment for powerful mathematical learning.

Format of the Study

This study was conducted in an all-boys school and a first class setting. The aim was to investigate the ways in which the children used representations to support reasoning, and to examine the roles of collaboration, and of the teacher in fostering reasoning. The work of two groups comprising ten children, was selected from whom to gather data as they engaged in a series of high-quality number tasks. Working in small groups, the boys were encouraged to record their solution attempts using the familiar representations of grouped and ungrouped base ten materials, counters, the empty number line, as well as pencil and paper and mental methods. Data sources included audio-recordings of children's interactions among their groups and with their teacher, work samples, researcher field notes and a reflective journal. The intention was to gather data across a period of five weeks, however the government-mandated closure of schools in response to the emerging COVID 19 first wave meant that data collection abruptly ceased after two weeks. Notwithstanding this, analysis of the available data sources allowed for an appropriate treatment of the research questions and for the emergence of some not entirely expected features.

Discussion

The examples presented below are chosen to demonstrate instances where children, engaging in quality collaborative tasks supported by access to representations and careful

teacher questions, were able to move among representations to explore and express mathematical ideas and to evaluate their choices in connection to others children's representations, and in some cases to their own limitations. In addition, some examples are presented in which children evaluated the available representations in terms of their suitability for the task at hand. In all cases, pseudonyms are used.

Evaluating Strategies in Peer Discussion

An indication of meaningful interaction both with the representation and the classroom discourse to refine thinking (Chapin et al, 2009) is exemplified in the task "True or false?" where children were asked to demonstrate whether double digit computations were correct. Different approaches using the same representation – the empty number line provided opportunities for children to display their mathematical thinking. Henry initially began by using an empty number line in single jumps (units) for the calculation $46 + 23 = 69$. In figure 1 below Henry adopted a 'count by ones' approach, while Andrew partitioned into tens to create more efficient jumps and modelled his approach to the group. In whole-class discussion, swift consensus was reached that Henry's approach was 'effective'. Now aware of the disadvantages of his chosen method, Henry altered his approach to incorporate his knowledge of place value to make his number line more efficient. His comment "Yeah, I'm doing jumps of tens. I forgot them, that's why I was taking so long. That's why Andrew finished before me!" shows his adoption of a more sophisticated way to manipulate the representation and his reliance on a peer to make this apparent. Interacting with the familiar representation allowed him to explore the mathematics, but the refining of the strategy was the result of seeing, discussing and evaluating his peer's approach in comparison to his own (Walshaw and Anthony, 2008).

Figure 1

Henry and Andrew's Approach to Proving an Addition Calculation

Flexibility in Approaches

Children proved very capable of using and rationalising varying strategies based on the numbers in a calculation. Although Andrew had initially used a number line to add, when working on a subtraction calculation in a similar numerical range, he chose to calculate in his head using mental representations of place value. He explained, "The units are the same so I can just get rid of them and count back the tens." Here he demonstrates he is able to reason his choice of selected method based on its effectiveness in the context of the problem. In addition to evaluating their reasoning in the context of the representations, the children also showed

insight into their own inclinations and needs for support from representations (Walshaw and Anthony, 2008). For example, Roger used partitioning as part of an informal approach to addition. He partitioned the 2 digit numbers into tens and units. Adding the tens, then the units and then recombining, claiming “I don’t need the number line to keep track.” Andrew explained, I did a number line so I don’t get confused.” Varying degrees of reasoning reflected the children’s stage of understanding, “I used a number line because that’s the one I like. I like it ‘cause you can see where you are” (Henry). Henry chose to rely on a number line as it was the most familiar and enabled him to keep track of his work whereas Terry considered the efficiency of the approach, “I used place value because that’s the quickest for me. I did it in my head” as did Andrew: “I used place value for my jumps because it’s quicker when you have bigger numbers”. Methods were chosen based on their perceived usefulness whether it was the support of a number line or the efficiency of a mental approach (Fuson et al., 2005). The range of approaches adopted by the children and the flexibility throughout the reasoning activities made it clear that they reasoned with strategies or approaches selected to suit at some times the context and at others their aptitudes and abilities.

Children were able to evaluate strategies and resources based on their relevance to the task at hand, using different approaches to solve and check the calculations provided with the efficiency of methods and resources also considered. Boaler et al, (2017) suggests that fluency with known facts and ideas can assist children’s ability to reason numerically. The examples above provide insight into children with varying levels of acquired facts, which is exposed in the differing levels of support sought from the representations as opposed to reasoning mentally. The different and changing approaches used demonstrate the children show insight into the personal *and* mathematical factors influencing their choice of method or representation and can understand that there are multiple approaches that can be used to solve the calculations (Fuson et al., 2005). The speed and efficiency advantage to some children of using flexible number sense approaches was stated alongside frank acknowledgement by others of the benefit of using an empty number line in terms of providing clarity and guarding against confusion.

Evaluating the Utility of Representations

A particularly interesting aspect of reasoning which arose was the children’s evaluation of representations in the context of the task, and their awareness of the mathematical limitations and affordances of various representations. The role of the teacher was key here in sparking at least some of these discussions. Two examples are presented below:

- Teacher: Is the 20 frame helpful here?
Kelvin: Not really.
Teacher: Why not? What would be helpful?
Jim: Cause it’s a 20 frame and that’s 2 ten frames but we need 3 groups.
Kelvin: You could use groups of 10 (Dienes blocks).
Jim: Yeah, you can’t stack that many blocks.

In the above brief excerpt, the teacher's suggestion is rejected on valid grounds, and the children can volunteer both a suitable and unsuitable alternative. The children are not merely evaluating the mathematics in terms of the representations (Kaput, 1991), but they are evaluating the representations in terms of the mathematics. Once again, just as they displayed flexibility in approaches above, they display flexibility in choosing useful tools for representation, choosing and rejecting them as the task demanded. Below we see that Ed is just as able to spot the limitations of Dienes blocks for this task as Kelvin was to see their benefit in the previous example.

- Teacher: How could we use them then to find all our combinations?
- Jim: You can split them and turn them into different ones.
- Ed: That's why you don't use blocks of ten. You can't split them. You need to use counters.
- Jim: Yeah, you can make more numbers if you use the counters.

In these examples, where the children evaluated and refined their representation methods in peer discussion; responding to and building on each other's statements provided them with opportunities to construct and refine their understanding (Brophy 2001). The conversations here are not influenced by personal preference for efficiency or stability offered by the one or the other method, but are squarely on the suitability of the tool to adequately represent the mathematics. The only distinction was on how the representations lent themselves to the task

Conclusions

The above features of the children's reasoning exemplify the complexity of developing the practice. The range of approaches adopted by the children and the flexibility throughout the reasoning activities made it clear that working on the tasks required more of them than consideration of the mathematics, but necessitated reflection on the problem and the selection of an appropriate way to represent it. Fuson (1988) suggests that children's number sense develops as they acquire the ability to be flexible with numbers. It had been anticipated that the children would engage with the resources, choosing and appropriately using them as tools to think with. However, the insight into the connections between their choice of representation and the level of support they required from it was a level of metacognition that was not foreseen. In addition, considering and evaluating the usefulness of the resources within the contexts of the tasks had not been anticipated, nor flagged in literature sources consulted. The children demonstrated they were capable of reflecting on their own and others thinking by evaluating and critiquing the strategies and resources being used. Beyond that, they showed insight into how these strategies were appropriate to their own preference and perhaps state of learning; and how the available resources aligned with the mathematical demands of the task. In this process that appears to have been supported by the teacher who questioned the children's approaches and provided with opportunities to describe and justify thoughts and actions (Katz, 2014). Moreover, attention was frequently drawn to the ways students were thinking about their approach and solution to generate shared understandings (Boaler et al., 2018).

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